

Autobiographies of Inspirational Indian Personalities: Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, Sachin Tendulkar, M.C. Mary Kom

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Abstract:

The purpose of this paper presentation is to examine the autobiographical narratives of three well-known individuals: M.C. Mary Kom in Unbreakable, Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam in Wings of Fire, and Sachin Tendulkar in Playing It My Way. These autobiographies provide insightful accounts of the struggles, triumphs, and lives of people who have made a lasting impression on their respective fields. Dr A.P.J. Abdul Kalam describes in Wings of Fire how he rose from modest beginnings in Rameswaram to become one of the most renowned scientists and statesmen in India. Kalam shares the socioeconomic struggles he faced, the transforming power of education, and his unwavering commitment to serving his country through insightful reflections and vivid anecdotes.

Playing It My Way offers a first-hand account of the cricketing journey of the legendary cricketer, Sachin Tendulkar. In his autobiography, Tendulkar talks about his love of cricket, his unwavering ambition to be the best, and the life-changing lessons he learned from his cricketing and non-cricket life. He also talks about how cricket is a universal sport and how it shapes the identity and pride of a nation.

In M. C. Mary Kom's autobiography, Unbreakable, we get to see the story of the Manipuri boxer and the challenges she faced as a woman. Through her story, we learn about gender dynamics and social barriers, as well as her experiences of poverty and discrimination. In her story, Mary Kom shows us the resilience, perseverance, and the strength of self-confidence. Through cross-referencing, this paper will focus on common themes and themes of these autobiographies, including perseverance, the quest for perfection, and the transformative power of passion and commitment. In sum, this paper aims to highlight the richness and variety of autobiographical literature, while celebrating the inspiring stories of Dr A.P. J. Abdul Kalam, Sachin Tendulkar, and M. C. Mary Kom. Not only do their autobiographies provide readers with a glimpse into their personal lives, but they also serve as a source of inspiration and confidence for audiences around the world.

Keywords: autobiography, gender dynamics, poverty, discrimination, perseverance, perfection, challenges etc.

Introduction to Autobiography:

As a literary genre, autobiography has a special place in the vast world of literature. It provides an intimate and personal insight into the lives of real people. It allows readers to immerse themselves in the triumphs, tribulations, and changes of real people. What is Autobiography? Autobiographies are stories written by the people themselves. They tell the story of their experiences, their memories, and their thoughts. At its core, autobiography is self-expression. It is a way for people to tell their stories, their ideas, and who they are. Whether they are describing moments of happiness and success or facing challenges and adversity, they invite you to share in the rich and complex human experience.

The genre of autobiography is one that is not limited by space, time, or culture. It emphasizes the universal ideas and feelings that unite all people while also celebrating the individuality of every life. Let's embrace the diversity and complexity of human tales as we begin this examination of autobiographical literature and acknowledge the transforming power of the written word to enlighten, inspire, and bring people together.

***Wings of Fire* by Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam:**

Wings of Fire is more than just an autobiography; it's a monument to the ability to overcome socioeconomic obstacles with tenacity, knowledge, and resolve. The story of Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam is primarily based on his childhood in Rameswaram, a small village in Tamil Nadu, India. His parents instilled in him a strong sense of values and ethics despite many obstacles. Kalam's autobiography describes his family's hardships, who came from a low-income background, in great detail. He describes times when people were struggling financially and the creative ways they managed to get it. Many Indians from similar circumstances can relate to his experiences, which underscores the systemic socioeconomic divide that exists in the country.

Education's capacity to transform is one of *Wings of Fire's* main themes. Despite having few resources, Kalam's desire to learn kept him moving forward. His remarkable path from impoverished beginnings to become a world-renowned scientist and, ultimately, the President of India, highlights the significance of having access to high-quality education as a method of achieving social mobility and empowerment. In his autobiography, Kalam highlights the value of tenacity and fortitude in the face of difficulty. He tells stories of how obstacles and

disappointments made him more determined to go after his goals. Readers are encouraged to keep going after their goals in spite of setbacks by his unwavering desire to overcome hurdles. Beyond his own experience, Kalam describes his goals for the advancement of India.

In order to advance the country, he supports investing in science and technology, utilizing the potential of young people, and encouraging innovation. His forward-thinking concepts are still relevant to both citizens and government, influencing the conversation on India's development trajectory.

Kalam demonstrated moral leadership both in his role as a scientist and as the President of India. Throughout his story, he highlights the value of honesty, modesty, and service to humanity. His dedication to moral standards and ideals emphasizes the value of moral behavior in public life and governance, acting as a beacon of hope for those in positions of power.

Playing It My Way by Sachin Tendulkar:

Playing It My Way provides readers with an engrossing look into the life and career of Sachin Tendulkar, one of cricket's greatest legends. Tendulkar shares insights into his path from a young child with aspirations of playing cricket to becoming an icon admired by millions worldwide through his autobiography.

In his autobiography, Tendulkar explores the personal struggles he overcame to become a cricket superstar. Tendulkar's story is a monument to his tenacity and resolve in conquering challenges, from his early battles with homesickness at cricket academies to the weight of bearing the dreams of a nation on his shoulders. Tendulkar's persistent love for cricket and his unyielding work ethic are at the heart of *Playing It My Way*. He shares details about his exercise routine, mental preparedness, In addition to detailing Tendulkar's personal journey, *Playing It My Way* considers his wider influence on Indian culture and cricket as a whole. Beyond the cricket pitch, Tendulkar has inspired millions of aspiring players and acted as an inspiration for upcoming generations.

Unbreakable by M.C. Mary Kom:

Unbreakable offers readers a close-knit and motivational glimpse into the life of M.C. Mary Kom, one of the world's most accomplished female boxers. Mary Kom describes in her autobiography how she rose from impoverished Manipur, India, to become an Olympic bronze

medallist and six-time World Amateur Boxing champion. Mary Kom's account of her life's challenges and victories is a major component of *Unbreakable*. Mary Kom's story, which includes her upbringing in poverty and her battles with discrimination and social barriers as a female athlete in a male-dominated field, is an inspiration to anyone who values resiliency and dedication above all else. The autobiography of Mary Kom provides insights into her intense love of boxing and her unwavering quest for perfection in the sport. She talks about the difficult training schedule she followed, the sacrifices she made, and the difficulties she faced before winning the world championship. Her many honors and accomplishments are proof of her unmatched talent, athleticism, and dedication to her art.

Mary Kom, one of the most well-known athletes in India, considers her role as a pioneer and an encouragement to young athletes, particularly those who identify as women. She hopes to motivate and inspire readers to follow their aspirations with courage through her autobiography, regardless of their gender, background, or social expectations. Mary Kom's tale highlights the common characteristics of bravery, and resilience. It crosses boundaries and connects with people all across the world. "Unbreakable" also clarifies Mary Kom's support of social change and women's liberation. She aspires to build a more inclusive and equitable society for coming generations by using her position as a well-known athlete to promote topics like gender equality, health awareness, and education. Mary Kom's activism goes beyond the boxing ring, proving her dedication to changing the world in addition to her sporting accomplishments.

Comparative Analysis of Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, Sachin Tendulkar, and M.C. Mary Kom in Their Autobiographies:

Background and Upbringing: Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam was raised in a close-knit neighborhood and was taught values by his parents. He was born into a modest household in Rameswaram, as described in his autobiography, *Wings of Fire*.

Sachin Tendulkar: Tendulkar is a Mumbai native. In his autobiography, *Playing It My Way*, he talks of his early love of cricket and his family's fostering of his gift.

M.C. Mary Kom: Born and raised in Manipur, Kom's autobiography, *Unbreakable*, describes her childhood in a place beset by socioeconomic hardships as well as the difficulties she encountered as a female athlete in a sport dominated by men.

Journey to Success:

Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam's tenacity, devotion to learning, and love for serving his nation have all contributed to his success. Overcoming socioeconomic obstacles, he rises to prominence as a scientist and finally assumes the role of 11th President of India.

Sachin Tendulkar: Tendulkar's autobiography details his ascent to cricketing fame, emphasizing his love for the sport, unwavering work ethic, and a plethora of on-field accomplishments. He rises to prominence in Indian cricket and is admired for both his skill and his sportsmanship.

M.C. Mary Kom: The autobiography of Kom tells the story of her incredible journey from a small Manipur town to the title of world boxing champion. She defies expectations set by society, triumphs over financial hardships and gender discrimination, and achieves unparalleled success in her sport.

Challenges Faced: Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam: Kalam has to deal with issues like poverty, resource scarcity. Nevertheless, he is able to overcome these challenges and follow his dreams because of his tenacity and resolve.

Sachin Tendulkar: Throughout his career, Tendulkar has battled injuries, the duties of professional cricket, and the expectations of stardom. He keeps his goals in mind and performs well on the field in spite of setbacks.

M.C. Mary Kom: Kom faces discrimination based on gender, financial hardships, and a lack of encouragement for female athletes in India. She continues to pursue excellence in spite of these obstacles, setting an example for upcoming generations of female boxers.

Impact and Legacy: Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam: Kalam faces challenges such as poverty, limited available resources, and societal expectations. However, his will power and determination enable him to overcome these obstacles and pursue his dreams.

Sachin Tendulkar: Tendulkar has struggled with injuries, the demands of playing professional cricket, and the demands of being a celebrity throughout his career. In spite of failures, he remains focused on his objectives and plays effectively on the field.

Mary Kom: M.C. Kom has to deal with financial difficulties, gender discrimination, and a lack of support for female athletes in India. Despite these challenges, she keeps going after greatness, leading by example for future generations of female boxers.

Conclusion: Despite the fact that Dr. A.P.J. Abdul Kalam, Sachin Tendulkar, and M.C. Mary Kom have different origins and follow various career trajectories, their autobiographies have a lot in common, including tenacity, willpower, and the transformational potential of passion. They leave behind enduring legacies that continue to influence and inspire generations through their narratives, which also serve as a source of inspiration for readers with their personal stories. Autobiographies are priceless windows into society's heart and soul; they are reflections of the human condition in a wide range of settings, civilizations, and historical periods. Through critical engagement with these personal narratives, we can probe the present, expand on our understanding of the past, and explore possibilities for the future.

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